

Is there an effective pharmacotherapy for COVID-19?

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Coronaviruses are important human and animal pathogens. At the end of 2019, a novel coronavirus was identified as the cause of a cluster of pneumonia cases in Wuhan, a city in the Hubei Province of China. It rapidly spread, resulting in an epidemic throughout China, followed by an increasing number of cases in other countries throughout the world. In February 2020, the World Health Organization designated the disease COVID-19, which stands for coronavirus disease 2019. The virus that causes COVID-19 is designated severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2); previously, it was referred to as 2019-nCoV. Despite the availability of various COVID-19 vaccines and intensive vaccine campaign, the search for effective pharmacotherapy must not stop, especially because of the emergence of new SARS-CoV-2 strains that are more or less resistant to up to date available vaccines.

Caffeic Acid

Caffeic acid is pharmacologically active compound of many medicinal herbs such as *Echinacea purpurea* and *Sambucus Formosana Nakai*. Based on the up to date published scientific reports caffeic acid could be a potent molecule for the treatment of COVID-19, especially if paired with Fe³⁺ ions (caffeic acid Fe³⁺ chelate) or other ions (MoO₄²⁻ and PO₄³⁻ chelates), because antiviral activity of caffeic acid increases upwards of 100-fold by the addition of cations (Fe³⁺) and anionic molecules (molybdate, phosphate). Caffeic acid and its derivatives may be used against the spread of SARS-CoV-2 and should be further tested as prophylaxis and treatment of COVID-19.

Glycyrrhizin

Based on the up to date published scientific reports glycyrrhizin from liquorice root could be used as therapeutic for COVID-19 (both as oral preparation and as nasal spray) and as a preventive agent against the spread of SARS-CoV-2. Glycyrrhizin has both antiviral and

antioxidant activity and thus, it can be useful molecule for the prevention and treatment of cytokine storm.

Antibiotics with inhibitory effect on SARS-CoV-2

Based on the up to date published in-silico studies and few clinical reports promising antibiotic agents that could exert inhibitory effect on SARS-CoV-2 are **rifampicin, doxycycline, cefuroxime, ciprofloxacin and moxifloxacin**. Further clinical research is mandatory to determine the clinical efficacy and dose regimen of these antibiotics for the treatment of symptomatic COVID-19 patients. These antibiotics could be especially useful in patients with COVID-19 pneumonia with bacterial co-infection or superinfection.

Formoterol

Formoterol is a long-acting β_2 agonist (LABA) used as a bronchodilator in the management of asthma and COPD. The results of two studies suggest that inhaled formoterol might be used as additional therapeutic agent in the treatment of COVID-19, especially in patients with asthma or COPD. Liang and coworkers published a COVID-19 case coexisting with severe asthma. Budesonide/glycopyrrolate/formoterol fumarate (BGF) was used as sequential medicine to systemic glucocorticoids for his persisted symptoms related to bronchospasms. Authors concluded that BGF is able to be an effective and convenient choice as sequential medicine to systemic glucocorticoids in some refractory asthmatic patients complicated with COVID-19.

Probiotics

Probiotics are generally considered safe. There is a good scientific evidence to support the ability of probiotics to boost human immunity. It is rationale to support the use of probiotics in prevention and treatment of viral infections, including COVID-19. In addition to that, the use of probiotics in COVID-19 can serve as protective factor against cytokine storm and consequential autoimmunity.

Quercetin

Quercetin, a naturally occurring dietary flavonoid, is well known to ameliorate chronic diseases and aging processes in humans, and its antiviral properties have been investigated in numerous studies. Quercetin supplementation together with multivitamin and trace elements supplementation (especially vitamins C and D, zinc) can be useful in prophylaxis and treatment of mild symptomatic COVID-19 patients, but more clinical research is mandatory to determine the exact clinical efficacy and dose regimen.

Resveratrol

Resveratrol (from grape seeds and red wine) is an interesting molecule for further research on SARS-CoV-2 because it has been found that it has some in vitro anti-viral effect on coronaviruses. Based on the available up to date published research resveratrol can be used alone or in combination with trace elements (copper, zinc) in prophylaxis and/or treatment of COVID-19, but more clinical investigation is necessary to determine the exact clinical efficacy and precise dose regimen.

Bismuth complexes

Based on the up to date published scientific reports one of the possible drug candidates for the treatment of COVID-19 are bismuth complexes.

Gelomyrtol

Considering the wide spectrum of antimicrobial and antioxidant activity of Gelomyrtol® Forte capsules (mixture of purified essential oils of eucalyptus, sweet orange, myrtle and lemon) along with secretolytic and secretomotor activity it might be used as additional therapeutic agent in COVID-19 pneumonia with or without bacterial superinfection.

CytoSorb therapy

It is documented in the literature that critically ill patients with COVID-19 had the increased levels of many proinflammatory cytokines. Based on the up to date published clinical experiences on the use of CytoSorb therapy for COVID-19 patients developing cytokine storm, CytoSorb cartridge provided a safe rescue therapy in life-threatening COVID-19.

Dabigatran etexilate

As dabigatran is both anticoagulant and potential SARS-CoV-2 inhibitor based on virtual screening results, it could be a new therapeutic option for the prophylaxis and treatment of COVID-19 associated thromboembolism, but further clinical research is mandatory.

Rosuvastatin

Based on *in silico* studies statins could be efficient SARS-CoV-2 Mpro inhibitors, especially rosuvastatin. It has been also showed that rosuvastatin can significantly decrease the rate of deep vein thrombosis (JUPITER trial), and that it can improve lung pathological changes by decreasing T helper cells Th2 and Th17-mediated cytokines. Therefore, rosuvastatin might be an useful adjunct therapy in patients with COVID-19, especially in those who already have an

indication for statin use (homozygous familial hypercholesterolemia, hyperlipidemia, mixed dyslipidemia, primary dysbetalipoproteinemia, hypertriglyceridemia, prevention of cardiovascular disease).

Pentoxifylline

Because of the antiviral, anti-inflammatory, anti-oxidative, immune-modulatory, bronchodilator and respiratory supportive effects, protective roles in organ failures, along with its main functions means better circulation-oxygenation properties, low price and safety, pentoxifylline is now being investigated in a clinical trial as a multipurpose and generally-safe adjuvant therapy for COVID-19 patients. Pentoxifylline might also be considered as prophylactic and protective therapy during the COVID-19 pandemic era in patients who already have label or off-label indications for its use (intermittent claudication caused by chronic occlusive arterial disease of the limbs, cerebrovascular disease, Behcet's disease, congestive heart failure, vascular disorder of inner ear, venous stasis ulcer of leg, diabetes mellitus, non-alcoholic fatty liver disease, Peyronie's disease).

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